

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN GAS EXTRACTION - EFFICIENCY FOUNDATION

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Abstract: *This article discusses the problem and task of extracting gas and gas condensate from new and depleted fields through the introduction of innovative technologies and scientific recommendations.*

Key Words: *Reservoir, well, drilling, productive layer, layering, geological exploration, innovation, pressure compressor station, sour gas, geological-technological.*

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Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматривается проблема и задача добычи газа и газового конденсата из новых и из истощенных месторождений путем внедрения инновационных технологий и научных рекомендаций.*

Ключевые слова: *Запас, скважина, бурение, продуктивный пласт, освоение пласта, геологоразведка, инновация, дожимная компрессорная станция, кислый газ, геолого-технологический.*

Introduction. The oil and gas industry of Uzbekistan is a developed industry that produces a spectrum of high-quality products. According to experts' estimates, the amount of fuel and mineral resources of Uzbekistan is 3 trillion. dollar and hydrocarbon reserves make an average of three parts of all reserves of Central Asia. So it goes without saying that in the next 100-year development of the oil and gas industry, the main task is to reconstruct and modernize the technological processes in the enterprises and to use modern techniques and technologies effectively.

Along with the increasing demand for natural gas and its products, the demand for increased gas processing and extraction is also increasing. This requires a more serious and accurate approach to the gas production process. In increasing and developing gas production, it is important not only to study foreign experiences, but also to apply, use and implement advanced innovative technologies in oil and gas production.

"Intelligent" approach to gas production development processes, starting with reserve identification, drilling wells, extraction, development of productive layers and using wells using efficient and advanced technologies, using innovative and computer technologies and special programs and programs for the system of collecting and preparing products. and application of effective projects has become the need of the hour today.

According to the program of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan RU No. PP 2822 approved on March 9, 2018, natural gas production will increase by 1.3 times in 2017-2021.

This automatically set the oil and gas industry specialists specific tasks that should be performed with speed and precision (operationally).

Main part. In order to solve the tasks in a practical and positive way, first of all, it is necessary to recalculate the amount of reserves in the working mines, to carry out geological-exploration works in the mines (GRR), and secondly, to launch the facilities using new innovative technologies for natural gas extraction, and to perform the following issues together. [1-2]

1. Due to the step-by-step application of modern innovative technologies in order to achieve a high gas production coefficient (GRP) in fields that have been used for many years.
2. The following innovative solutions are recommended in order to immediately reduce the period (time) of the newly launched mines and to achieve the planned goal:

It is necessary to transfer the use of wells in used gas and gas condensate deposits (50% of the recoverable reserves have been mined) to the compressor method, to build compression compressor stations (DKS) operating at low inlet pressure. The sooner the compression compressor station is built in the gas and gas condensate fields, the more efficiently the reserves that can be extracted from the deposits will be extracted. [5-6]

When the operating index of the (desired) deposits used in the last periods of their operation is equal to $K_{\text{ИГ}} \geq 0.65$, for the prospective use of the deposit in the future, it is possible to use systems that work in sources of low pressure:

- use as a source of raw materials in gas refueling facilities (AGNKS) in cases where there is no gold-sulfur in the gas;
- the use of high-power modern mobile compressors in extracting gas from fields containing sour gases (Mubarak gas processing plant, Shurtan gas chemical complex).

Another important aspect of the use of innovative technologies in natural gas production is that the techniques and technologies of working mines can be used in the operation of redevelopment mines due to the joint operation of mines (exploration and operation periods):

- it is possible to shorten the periods of exploitation of mines that are being newly started, due to the joint operation of mines (exploration and exploitation periods);
 - at the expense of restarting the wells in the temporarily closed fields, it is possible to purposefully use the gas extracted from the exploration wells, where there are industrially significant reserves in the fields, for example, for the internal consumption of neighboring fields located nearby.

The proposed innovative recommendations to increase and accelerate natural gas production have shown their effectiveness and results in specific facilities. After gas condensate fields of Gazli, Shurtan, Zevarda, Alat, Kultak, Pamuk, Southern Kemachi, Kukdumalak were used by compressor method, with the help of compression compressor stations (DKS), the gas production coefficient (GER) from the fields increased significantly. Another solution is the effective and targeted use of additional extracted residual gas.

From the developed recommendations for increasing natural gas extraction, scientific research and test-design works were carried out in the fields of the last period of this use (Shortepa, South and North Mubarak, Karakum, Khodjikhayram, Shumak) and practical recommendations were given (Shevtsov et al., "OZLITINEFTGAZ" JSC, Tashkent 2008):

- restart wells in gas and gas condensate fields that are temporarily closed due to various geological and technological reasons;
- connecting the wells to the collection system of the working mines located in the vicinity and connecting them to work.

The use of the results of the experiments of the restarted mines in the process of drawing up the commissioning projects of the Arslan and Inam gas condensate fields, which are being tested and explored in the Ustyurt oil and gas area, not only allows to speed up the time of commissioning of these fields, but also shows its effectiveness.

The Arslan gas condensate field was opened in 2015, and the field is located in the Muynak district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Arslan GKK No. 1 well was opened with a gas flow of 582,000 m³/day as a result of research carried out in the perforation intervals of 3337-3304 m. According to the results of geological prospecting (GRR), the gas condensate reserve on an industrial scale is lower terrigenous (J₁¹, J₁⁴, J₁^{4a}, J₁⁵, J₁^{5a}, J₁⁶, J₁^{6a} horizons) in the middle jurassic (J₂¹¹, J₂¹², J₂¹⁴⁶, J₂¹⁷⁶ horizons) determined. The fund of wells is presented in (table 1).

Arslan GKK wells fund as of 01.01.2020

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Category of wells	Number of wells	Number of wells
Total, incl	7	1,2,3,4,5,6,8
in motion	6	1,2,3,4,5,8
son	1	6
In addition	4	7,11,17,21
In addition	4	7,11,17,21

As mentioned above, as a result of the geological-geophysical research carried out in the Arslan and Inam mines, it was determined that there are effective gas flows in the layers, and test-industrial and equipment projects for the use of the mine were developed. According to the developed design documents (Karshiev A et al. IGIRNIGM 2015), it is recommended to connect the wells of these mines to the collection point (SP) in the North Berdak mine.

The Inam gas condensate mine was opened in 2014, and the mine is located in the Muynoq district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The structure of the Inam mine is located in the western-eastern part of the sea bends, that is, in the area where prospecting works are being carried out at a rapid pace, around a number of North Berdak-Berdak, Sharkiy Berdak and other mines.

The Inam gas condensate field was studied during geological exploration and the amount of gas condensate on an industrial scale was determined as a result of research conducted in exploration wells No. 1, 2, 3. The operational gas reserve is determined by the quantitative method given in the literature [4], by the following formula [1].

$$Q_r = S \cdot h \cdot K_{\Pi} \cdot K_r \cdot (P_{\Pi\Pi} \cdot \alpha_{\Pi\Pi} - P_0 \cdot \alpha_0) \cdot f \cdot \eta \quad (1)$$

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Here S is gas area, thousand. m^2 ; h – effective gas saturated thickness m , K_{π} – coefficient of porosity, K_r – gas saturation coefficient, $P_{\text{пл}}$, P_0 – boshlangych va akhergi katalam barefoot ($P_0=1$); $\alpha_{\text{пл}}$, α_0 – Boiler-Mariotte of real gases ($\alpha_0 = 1$) some amendments according to the law, f – correction for temperature, η - recalculated coefficient of dry gas. Filtration resistance values as a result of hydrodynamic studies $A= 53,116$ ва $B= 0,1789$ It was determined that.

According to the document indicated in the current status of the Inam field [3-4], it is envisaged to use 300 million cubic meters of gas per year with a maximum of 10 wells. [3-4]. 01.01.2020 4 exploratory wells have been drilled in the field of Inam GKK, 1 exploratory well No. 3 is used for gas production, the next well No. 2 is prepared for operation, well No. 1 is under repair (KRS), operational wells No. 11, 16 are being drilled, and the active well fund is listed. (table 2)

This is the GKK mining wells fund

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Years	Fund of moving wells		
	fact	project	Number of gas wells
2017	1	-	1
2018	1	4	1
2019	1	6	3

It can be seen from the table that during the mining test-industrial project (OPE) the project indicators lag behind the actual indicators.

Conclusion. Accelerated commissioning of the Arslan and Inam gas condensate fields is considered urgent today, as it is necessary to start the above-mentioned fields in order to continuously supply enterprises such as the Ustyurt gas chemical complex with raw materials.

The problem considered in the article and the obtained results show that the use of innovative technologies in gas production allows to increase the amount of gas production, to accurately and quickly determine the amount of residual and initial reserves in the fields, to create a database for drawing up projects for the development of mines, and to speed up the collection period. It is the basis for more effective use of the system of main gas pipelines and underground gas storage facilities and proper and efficient use of deposits.

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